

Special Relativity, Conservation Laws and Particle-Wave Duality Part 3 Energy as a State Variable?

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In Part 2, we suggested that both free particle and single particle bound state quantum mechanics seem to respect the classical notion of kinetic energy in the nonrelativistic case (at least within classical turning points for the latter), while not respecting $dx=v_{rms}(x) dt$. We consider this peculiar as $p^2/2m$ is the nonrelativistic kinetic energy associated with a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ and $\langle KE \rangle = \int \psi^* \hat{p} \psi dx / \int \psi^* \psi dx$ equivalent to $\langle p(x)p(x) \rangle / 2m$ holds for a single particle bound state (within classical turning points). As a result, we suggest that energy seems to be a state variable for a particle and that, like with thermodynamics quantities, one may calculate it using paths which are not necessarily the physical one which occurs.

In particular, a free particle is linked with $KE=p^2/2m$ which follows from a Newtonian approach: $m dv/dt = F \rightarrow \int m v dv = \int F dx$. This same free particle is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which we have called a signal probability wave which governs interference with 2-slits. If a quantum particle interacts as $\exp(ipx)$, then it does not seem to interact in the $\int m v dv$ Newtonian manner, but the kinetic energy as a state variable may be still represented by $.5mv^2$.

In the single particle bound state, $\exp(ipx)$ again is involved in interactions, thus one does not have the Newtonian process, even within classical turning points, but if kinetic energy is a state variable, like $V(x)$, then the particle must have $.5mv^2(x)$ at each x even if this created in a different manner the Newtonian acceleration in $dx \rightarrow 0$. One may see that the Newtonian approach does not hold in the quantum case as $\int P(x) dx$ is not equal to $C dt$ (C = normalization), but that one rather uses $\int W^*(x)W(x) dx$ as was discussed in Part 2. Nevertheless, KE (or energy in general) as a state variable must be consistent in the quantum and classical limit approaches, while $P(x)$ is not.

Newtonian Mechanics and Special Relativity

Newtonian mechanics utilizes the second law: $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ ((1)).

If: $m_0 dv/dt = F \rightarrow m_0 \int dv v = \int F dx = .5m_0 v^2$ ((2)) (for $v=0$ to v)

The Newtonian approach maps out a very specific path for achieving kinetic energy in the above example. Actually, one could have an impulse hit which interacts in a strange manner and the particle achieve kinetic energy $.5m_0 v^2$. We suggest that the kinetic energy is a state variable and the path of v to $v+dv$ etc in ((2)) is one possible way of achieving the $.5m_0 v^2$ endpoint.

To see the state variable scenario more clearly, we consider the complementarity of frames moving at constant $-v$ to each other of special relativity. A particle with rest mass in one frame is seen to be moving with v in the other (and vice versa) and mv may be considered as a kind of flux. Using this idea, one may create a matrix linking $(0, m_0)$ to (p, E) such that there is an equation linking these two sets of variables due to the complementarity of moving frames (at constant speed).

$$|g(v) - v/c g(v)| \quad ((3))$$

$$|vg(v) - g(v)|$$

$v g(v)$ appears in ((3)) to create a flux from m_0 . If one considers a modulus type relation, then:

$$-EE + ppcc = -m_0 m_0 c c c c \quad ((4)) \text{ from which } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$$

$$\text{In the nonrelativistic limit } v \ll c, \quad E = m_0 c c + .5 m_0 v v \quad ((5))$$

One may arrive at the state variable energy using the complementarity approach without any notion of the specific process required to accelerate the particle. We argue that this is an important feature because it seems that special relativity also gives rise to free particle quantum mechanics.

$$\text{Special relativity yields: } E = m_0 c c / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ and } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((6))$$

for a particle with rest mass m_0 . One may see that the speed c (upper bound speed which is the same in all frames) appears in ((6)). We suggest that there are then two solutions linked with ((6)). One is associated with center-of-mass motion and the other with signal c interactions. We suggest that:

$$-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0 \text{ applies to the center-of-mass and } -Et + px = 0 \text{ (like a photon) to the } c \text{ signal} \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that one has $\Delta t = \hbar/E$, $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ linked with an interaction. Experimentally, this is born out through the 2-slit experiment. The point we make is that even though the particle seems to interact through $\exp(ipx)$, which is nothing like $\int dv v m$, the kinetic energy associated with p (nonrelativistic) is still $pp/2m$. (We note that special relativity yields $\exp(ipx)$ for a constant p above.)

Application to a Bound State

We try to apply these ideas to a bound state. In Newtonian mechanics, one has $p(x)$ in each dx and an acceleration occurs in $dx \rightarrow 0$. This completely contradicts $\exp(ipx)$ if $\hbar/p > dx$. Nevertheless, $KE(x)$ in the Newtonian and quantum cases should be the same if $KE(x)$ (actually E) is a state variable. After all, for a very high energy level, the quantum case should merge into the classical. Even if one starts with $\exp(ipx)$ s to describe the quantum interaction with $V(x)$ (which is not the Newtonian interaction) one must still arrive at the same $KE(x)$. This can be done by forcing:

$$\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \ pp/2m \} / \{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E \quad ((8))$$

Physically one does not have a process at all similar to Newtonian mechanics (in the low energy level regime), but $\langle KE \rangle$ is nevertheless the same as it is a state variable.

One may see, however, that $dx = v_{rms}(x) dt$ which describes a classical kind of motion is not linked to $P(x) dx$ (where $P(x)$ is probability to be at x).

$$P(x) dx = W^*(x)W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

One cannot use the smooth acceleration scheme of Newton in an equation: $\int KE(x) P(x) dx$ because $P(x)$ is not a state variable. Rather in the high energy level limit:

$P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x)dx$ (using the envelope function of $W^*(x)W(x)$) should become equivalent to:

$$C dx / |v(x)| \text{ where } C \text{ is a normalization constant } ((10))$$

As a result, no state variable appears with $P(x)$, while it seems to be present for $KE(x)$ and E . One already sees this with special relativity for a constant v which yields $\exp(ipx)$ as well as $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that energy is a state variable. If that is the case, then different creation paths all lead to the same energy as different paths (including a quasistatic ones) lead to the same state variables as in thermodynamics. In particular, $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ (nonrelativistic) follows from the process: $dp/dt = F \rightarrow \int m_0 v dv = \int F dx$, but physically such a smooth change may not occur. We argue that one may see energy appear as a state variable by considering special relativity which yields $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ without any force-acceleration process being considered. Furthermore, we argue that special relativity yields $\exp(ipx)$ as a signal-c interaction probability.

Thus, one has the state variable $p^2/2m$, but the particle interacts as $\exp(ipx)$ (as in a 2-slit experiment) and not at all like $\int m_0 v dv$. This becomes more relevant if one considers an interaction with a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, it is again $\exp(ipx)$ s which interact with $V(x)$ which is completely un-Newtonian, but if $KE(x)$ is a state variable, these $\exp(ipx)$ s must create an average KE which matches the classical $p(x)p(x)/2m$. In other words, for any energy level: $p(x)p(x)/2m = \{ \sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$. This does not mean that one has classical motion because $P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x)dx$ and this is not linked with $dx = v_{rms}(x)dt$ except for very high energy levels, i.e. in the classical regime. Thus, $P(x)$ is not a state variable, while energy is (as already seen in special relativity, we argue.)